

The role and importance of "Data Science" in the world

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13335060>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 30-iyun 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 9-iyul 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 20-iyul 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

*Data Science, computer
science, artificial intelligence,
Committee on Data.*

ABSTRACT

*In this article, the history of the origin of the field
of Data Science, its place in the world community, and
various comments on this field are mentioned.*

It is no secret that today the world of technology is rapidly developing. One of the necessary fields in the age of science and technology is Data Science. Informatics and information technologies are entering almost all fields, and, of course, in harmony with modern technologies, the profession of Data Science is also developing and improving day by day.

Data Science is a field of computer science that studies the problems of analyzing, processing and presenting data in digital form. Also, this field combines large-scale and high-level data processing methods, static methods, data mining methods, and artificial intelligence (AI) programs for working with data, as well as database design and development methods.

If we look at the history of Data Science, we can see how young it is. The beginning of the formation of this science is considered to be in 1966, when the Committee on Data (CODATA) was established, and the term Data Science was first used by Peter Naur in his book in 1974. However, this term became popular since 1990. The growth of interest in Data Science is associated with the emergence of the "Big Data" paradigm, which focuses on new technological possibilities for processing large-scale and diverse data. It can be seen that Data Science has rapidly developed in a short period of time and has been able to create its place on the world scale. In fact, the Data Science role was named the "Sexiest job of the 21st century" by the Harvard Business Review.

To study "Data Science" and become an expert in this profession, it is necessary to have a good knowledge of digital technologies, programming and mathematics. A Data Scientist processes data sets, finds new connections and patterns in them using machine learning algorithms, and creates models.

The global search engines, voice assistants, facial recognition services, recommendation services, autonomous trains and cars that have now become an integral part of our lives are all built with the help of data scientists.

From the above, it can be seen that the place of "Data Science" is of great importance in the whole world. Therefore, in order to widely develop the economy of our country, ample opportunities are being created for the next generation to learn knowledge and skills in Data

Science and to work more on their own in the field. Currently, experience working with real business projects is more important to an employer than a degree or specialized higher education. Therefore, it is necessary to attract more young people to future professions that can raise the country's economy to higher heights..

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